

MODELING THE LONG-TERM SIMULTANEITY OF DIVIDEND POLICY AND STOCK RETURN OF INSURANCE COMPANIES IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine whether the Current Ratio, Stock Price, Return on Assets, and Debt to Equity Ratio have a significant effect simultaneously on Dividend Policy. And to determine whether return on Assets, Debt to Equity Ratio, Return on Equity, and PER have a significant effect simultaneously on Stock Return. And by panel to find out whether Current Ratio, Stock Price, Return On Assets, Debt to Equity Ratio, Return On Equity, and PER have a positive partial and simultaneous effect on Stock Return. The present study is an associative/quantitative research. This study was conducted in insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the period 2012 – 2021. The method used in this research is Two-stage-least-square (2SLS), which is a special tool in instrumental variables regression. In the Panel method, panel regression is used to obtain the estimation results of each individual characteristic separately. The results in this study are equation I: $R^2 = 0.601129$ which means that the variables CR, HG, ROA, DER, and RSHM are able to explain KDIV by 60.1% and the remaining 39.9% is influenced by other variables outside the estimates in the model. And for equation II the result of the simultaneous method is $R^2 = 0.433269$ which means that the variables ROA, DER, ROE, PER, and KDIV are able to explain RSHM by 43.3% and the remaining 36.7% is influenced by other variables outside the estimation in the model. The leading indicators of Stock Return in insurance companies in Indonesia include PT. Asuransi Bina Dart, Tbk (ABDA), PT. Asuransi Harta Aman Pratama, Tbk (AHAP), PT. Asuransi Multi Arta Guna, (AMAG), PT. Asuransi Bintang, Tbk (ASBI), PT. Asuransi Jasa Tania, Tbk (ASJT), PT. Asuransi Ramayana, Tbk (ASRM), PT. Asuransi Dayin Mitra, Tbk (ASDM), PT. Lippo G Insurance, Tbk (LPGI), PT. Maskapai RI, Tbk (MREI), PT. Panin Insurance, Tbk (PNIN) and PT. Panin Life, Tbk (PNLF). Thus, on a panel basis, it turns out that all variables are able to become leading indicators in influencing stock returns in insurance companies in Indonesia in both short and long runs.

Keywords:dividend policy, stock return, insurance company

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid economic growth has forced many companies to carefully prepare new strategies that will be used as material for consideration in decision-making. Later this strategy is expected to have a positive impact on achieving the company's goals. Maximizing the value of shares is an important goal in establishing a company. Funds are a supporting factor in the ongoing operations of the company. One source of much-needed funds can be obtained from buying and selling shares in the capital market. Shares are ownership of companies that have legal force and can be traded. The number of shares held can determine the authority of an investor to manage and control the company.

There are many companies that have listed their companies on the capital market. The capital market is an exchange market where the securities traded reflect all the information that occurs quickly and accurately. According to Martalena and Malinda (2011), the capital market serves as a place that offers various financial instruments in the form of securities, namely stocks, warrants, bonds, mutual funds, and other securities.

The capital market plays a major role in the economy of a country because it carries out two functions at once, namely economics and finance. Listing companies in the capital market is a company strategy to obtain capital from external parties such as investors. Investors are individuals or institutions both domestic and non-domestic who make an investment (a form of investment according to the type of investment chosen) either in the short or long term.

The existence of investors who want to invest in a company has an impact on stable company funding. Investment is a commitment of a number of funds or other resources made at this time with the aim of obtaining profits in the future. Investors need information to find out the development of the company's issuers as consideration in determining how much property to invest. For investors, one of the information sources that can be used as the most accurate and complete source of information is the annual financial statement information. At least once a year, public companies are obliged to issue annual financial statement to investors on the stock exchange. In investing, investors really hope to get a high return from their investment.

Return is the reason someone invests in order to make a profit. The return that investors expect from their investment is compensation for the opportunity cost and the risk of a decline in purchasing power due to inflation.

The integrity of financial statement information that reflects the value of the company is a positive signal that can influence the opinions of investors and creditors or other interested parties. Financial statements should provide information that is useful for investors and creditors to make decisions about investments, credit, and the like. In Signalling Theory, investment spending emits a positive signal about the company's future growth, thereby increasing stock prices as an indicator of company value.

Investments that enter a company are used as funding capital in carrying out company operations to generate profits. From the net income obtained by the company, it will be distributed to investors in the form of capital gains or dividends or profits saved by the company, which will be used as a source of company funding in the next period for company development.

Capital gain or dividend is a gain or profit obtained from investment in securities in the property sector, where the value exceeds the purchase price. The difference between the higher selling price and the lower purchase price results in financial returns for investors. Determining the amount of dividends to be distributed to investors in the form of capital gains or dividends (yield) is the dividend policy of the company's leadership.

Dividend policy is a decision about whether the profits earned by the company will be distributed to shareholders as dividends or will be retained in the form of retained earnings to

finance investment in the future. Indirectly, information from dividend policy has an important role for investors. According to Sartono (2010: 281), information obtained about dividend policy is one of the determining factors in whether or not investors will invest funds again, and of course it will have an impact on the price of shares owned by the company.

Dividend policy is a policy that is implemented with quite expensive expenses, because the company must provide large amounts of funds for the purpose of paying dividends. Companies generally make stable dividend payments and refuse to reduce dividend payments. Only companies with high profits and bright future prospects are able to pay dividends. Many companies that always communicate that their company is prospective and face financial problems will certainly find it difficult to pay dividends. This has an impact on companies that distribute dividends, giving a sign to the market that the company has bright future prospects and is able to maintain the level of dividend policy that has been set in the previous period so that it will have a higher share price.

Insurance companies are institutions that provide various insurance policies to protect a person or their customers from various risks of loss by paying premiums regularly. Insurance companies operate by pooling the risks of a number of insurance policyholders. Insurance companies earn income from premium payments by customers. Insurance companies also get investment benefits derived from the investment of premiums received until they have to pay claims. For insurance companies, additional capital is needed to increase the capacity to bear the risk of their own policies.

Stock price is a very important price and must be considered by investors in investing. The value of shares is the right index of the effectiveness of a company so that it is often said to maximize the value of the company or maximize shareholder wealth. Thus, the higher the stock price, the higher the value of the company and vice versa. The development of stock prices of insurance industry companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2012 – 2021 can be seen in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1: Data on Share Prices of Insurance Companies for the Period 2012 – 2021

No.	Companies	Stock Prices (IDR) in Year									
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	PT. Asuransi Bina Darta, Tbk (ABDA)	1830	4250	6250	6825	6900	7250	6975	6975	5575	5850
2	PT. Asuransi Harta Aman Pratama, Tbk	190	168	240	220	195	195	85	60	70	74
3	PT. Asuransi Multi Arta Guna, (AMAG)	230	198	233	380	374	380	387	395	361	314
4	PT. Asuransi Bintang, Tbk (ASBI)	490	485	950	440	380	286	250	308	310	294
5	PT. Asuransi Jasa Tania, Tbk (ASJT)	276	140	294	157	210	650	360	119	200	139
6	PT. Asuransi Ramayana, Tbk (ASRM)	980	960	1285	2300	2690	2280	2350	2010	1970	1590
7	PT. Asuransi Dayin Mitra, Tbk (ASDM)	740	660	1150	1145	985	1015	1076	1096	985	950
8	PT. Lippo G Insurance, Tbk (LPGI)	1990	3275	4800	5250	5400	4870	4300	3600	3390	3880
9	PT. Maskapai RI, Tbk (MREI)	1710	2600	4240	6200	4250	4000	5100	4280	4700	4650
10	PT. Panin Insurance, Tbk (PNIN)	520	730	745	545	605	880	1050	1095	695	680
11	PT. Panin Life, Tbk (PNLF)	135	195	299	997	1145	248	268	302	246	172
	Average	826.45	1241.91	1862.36	2223.55	2103.09	2004.91	2018.27	1840.00	1682.00	1690.27

Source: sahamok.com/ processed data 2022

Based on Table 1.1, it can be seen that the average share price and the development of stock prices of each insurance company listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange show fluctuations every year. From the same table, it is also clear that there has been a sharp increase or decrease in stock prices. Note that ABDA and LPGI show high share price increases. This shows that the company is in a healthy condition and can be expected to have an impact on a high rate of return. However, apart from that, there were several other companies that experienced an increase and decrease in stock prices that were not stable. In such circumstances it can be indicated that the rate of return is low.

Figure 1: ROA of Insurance Companies in Period 2012 – 2021

From the graph in Figure 1.2 it can be seen that the ROA data fluctuates and in 2020 the ROA of PT. Asuransi Jasa Tania, Tbk (ASJT) showed a significant decline of -2.21%. For 4 consecutive years there has been a decline in ROA of PT. Safe Assets Insurance Pratama, Tbk and PT. Multi Arta Guna Insurance, Tbk.

In general, the main purpose of investors who invest their funds in a company is to seek a return on their investment. Bird in the Hand theory (Gordon & Lintner, 1961) states that some types of investors prefer to receive cash dividends that are certain to be received today than capital gains that are not certain to be received in the future (Halim, 2015: 138). Dividend payments reduce uncertainty because investors are more certain to receive dividend income compared to capital gains income. Return on Equity is part of the profit available to ordinary shareholders in cash (Warsono, 2003: 271).

Dividend distribution aims to maximize shareholder wealth and increase the value of the company. Companies tend to provide dividends with relatively stable amounts or increasing regularly (Atmaja, 2008: 290). Dividend stability can increase investor confidence in the company, thereby reducing investor uncertainty in investing their funds. Not all of the companies listed on the IDX are able to increase dividend distribution from year to year. The amount of the dividend payout ratio of all sectors listed on the IDX is as follows. The highest dividend payout ratio of all issuers listed on the IDX is indicated by the manufacturing sector. The manufacturing sector has dominated dividend distribution in the last five years with an average of 39.89%.

The manufacturing sector's ability to pay the highest dividends is inseparable from the industry's achievements in the midst of Indonesia's economic turmoil in 2014. The manufacturing industry in Indonesia continued to grow by 4.47% during 2014 compared to the previous year (ekbis.sindonews.com). The distribution of dividends is approved by all shareholders at the General Meeting of Shareholders (GMS) which is held to determine the amount of dividend payments. Dividend policy is a decision regarding the distribution of company profits at the end of the year to be distributed to shareholders in the form of dividends or to be retained to increase capital for investment financing in the future (Martono & Harjito, 2003: 253). Companies must think about saving costs and maximizing revenue so that they can earn profits to maximize owner wealth, employee welfare, and to develop business activities (Prawironegoro, 2010:4).

This shows that increasing profits can maximize shareholder wealth through distributed dividends. Dividends come from the company's net profit so that dividend policy can be influenced by the size of the company's profits. The company's profit is measured using a profitability ratio, one of which can use Return on Equity (ROE). ROE is the ratio of net income to equity, which measures the rate of return of shareholders (Brigham & Houston, 2010:149). ROE shows the company's ability to generate profits that can be distributed to shareholders. The greater the ROE, the better for the company because the company effectively uses equity to generate profits and vice versa. This is in accordance with the Signaling Hypothesis theory, which states that investors perceive dividend changes to be captured as a signal of good earnings in the future (Atmaja, 2008: 287). Therefore, the company will increase dividend payments if there is an increase in profit. Studies conducted by Elissya (2013) and Yudhanto & Aisjah (2011) in manufacturing companies prove that ROE has a significant positive effect on dividend policy (138 Journal of Business Economics Year 21, Number 2, October 2016). Based on these statements, hypothesis 1 can be formulated as: ROE has a significant positive effect on dividend policy. Dividend policy can also be influenced by the use of debt in the company.

Optimal use of debt can increase the company's operational activities so that it will generate a higher level of profit to be distributed to shareholders. However, the use of debt that is too large can reduce dividend payments because the company has to pay off the interest expense and principal of the loan when it is due. This condition refers to the Trade-Off theory (Modigliani & Miller, 1963) which states that companies cannot use debt as much as possible because the higher the debt, the higher the risk of default so the greater the possibility of bankruptcy (Hanafi, 2010: 309). Therefore, the amount of dividends to be distributed depends on the company's ability to manage its debt. The amount of the company's debt can be measured using the leverage ratio which is used to determine the extent to which the company can manage its debt portion well. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is one of the leverage ratios used to assess debt by equity (Kasmir, 2010: 112). DER reflects the company's ability to manage the portion of debt with the company's own capital.

The greater this ratio reflects the higher the company's financial risk, because the capital owned is not able to cover the company's debt. This condition is in accordance with the

Pecking Order theory (Myers, 1984), which states that dividend payments will reduce cash funds so that the company will use additional funds from debt (Hanafi, 2010: 314). The theory explains that the debt ratio is inversely proportional to profits, namely the higher the DER, the lower the profit so that the dividend is lower. Research conducted by Tania (2014) on manufacturing companies shows that DER has a significant positive effect on dividend policy. Research by Elissya (2013) on manufacturing companies and Rahmawati, et al (2015) on state-owned companies indicates that DER has a significant negative effect on DPR. Based on several statements stated above, hypothesis 2 can be formulated as: DER has a significant effect on dividend policy. The Signaling Hypothesis theory becomes a reference for investors because it contains information about the company's prospects in the future so that the company will continue to try to increase dividend payments from year to year.

The Maturity Hypothesis theory according to Grullon, et al (2002) in Darmawan (2011) suggests that long-established companies have low growth opportunities and fund little investment so that companies have the ability to distribute dividends in larger amounts. Companies that have been established for a long time are generally in the maturity stage, while companies that have not been established for a long time are in the growth stage. The age of the company describes how long the company has been operating since the company was founded. The age of the company is measured from (139 Rahmawati Dwika Pratiwi, Ely Siswanto, Lulu Nurul Istanti, Effect of Return on Equity, Debt) the year of research minus the year of company establishment (Margaretha & Ramadhan, 2010). According to Al-Makawi (2008) in Darmawan (2011), mature companies in the industry have the characteristics: 1) are large companies, 2) use low leverage, and 3) have high profitability, so that the company is a company that is able to pay dividends. A longer company age has the ability to generate profits from year to year and is able to minimize the risk of loss. Therefore, the effect of dividend policy that is influenced by ROE and DER can be strengthened or weakened by the age of the company. Research conducted by Darmawan (2008) found evidence that firm age has a significant positive effect on dividends. The meaning of the results of this study is that the longer the age of the company, the greater the company's ability to pay dividends. Based on the statements above, hypothesis 3 is formulated as follows: firm age moderates the effect of ROE on dividend policy and also hypothesis 4: firm age moderates the effect of DER on dividend policy.

The present study uses manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2014 as research subjects. The activity of a manufacturing company is to process raw materials into finished goods or produce a product that is ready to be sold. These companies include the basic and chemical industry sector, the miscellaneous industry sector, and the consumer goods industry sector. The purpose of this study was to determine the partial effect of ROE and DER on dividend policy and firm age as a moderating variable of the effect of ROE and DER on dividend policy.

This means that a decrease in earnings per share will affect the size of the dividend. If the profit earned is small, the company may not distribute dividends and make dividends as retained earnings in order to increase the company's ability. From the description above, the

authors are interested in conducting research using the insurance industry company as the object of research because the insurance sector is one of the businesses that has its own characteristics such as an underwriting function (risk management) and a claim handling function.

II. MATERIALS & METHOD

2SLS (Two Stage Least Square) Test by Simultaneous Analysis Model

The analytical model used is a system of simultaneous equations as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LOG(KDIV)} = & C(11)*\text{LOG(CR)} + C(12)*\text{LOG(HG)} + C(13)*\text{LOG(ROA)} + \\ & C(14)*\text{LOG(DER)} + \\ & C(15)*\text{LOG(RHSM)} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

KDIV = Dividend Policy (Billion Rp)

CR = Current Ratio (Percent)

HG = Stock Price (Million Rp)

ROA = Return On Asset (Percent)

DER = Debt Equity Ratio (Percent)

RHSM = Stock Return (Percent)

C(11), C(12), (13), = constants

$\alpha_0-\alpha_3$ = regression coefficients

e = term error

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LOG(RHSM)} = & C(21)*\text{LOG(ROA)} + C(22)*\text{LOG(DER)} + C(23)*\text{LOG(ROE)} + \\ & C(24)*\text{LOG (PER)} + C(25)*\text{LOG(KDIV)} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

RHSM = Stock Return (Percent)

ROA = Return On Asset (Percent)

DER = Debt Equity Ratio (Percent)

ROE = Return On Equity (Percent)

PER = Price Earnings Ratio (Percent)

KDIV = Dividend Policy (Billion Rp)

C(21), C(22), (23) = constants

$\alpha_0,\alpha_1,-\alpha_3,$ = regression coefficients

e = term error

ARDL Panel Test

This study uses panel data, namely data between times and data between regions. Panel regression is used to obtain the estimation results of each individual characteristic separately.

Panel Regression Test using the formula:

$$\text{Stock Return} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{CR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{HG}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ROA}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{DER}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{ROE}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{PER}_{it} + \epsilon$$

The following is the regression panel formula by Company:

$$\text{Stock Return of the Company (...) = } \alpha + \beta_1 \text{CR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{HG}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ROA}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{DER}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{ROE}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{PER}_{it} + \epsilon$$

Where:

CR = Current Ratio

HG = Stock Price

ROA = Return On Asset

DER = Debt to Equality Ratio

ROE = Return On Equity

PER = Price Earnings Ratio

ϵ = error term

β = regression coefficient

α = constant

i = number of observations

t = time

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results of Simultaneous Regression Test

Table 2: Simultaneous Test Results of Equation I

System: SIMULTAN				
Estimation Method: Two-Stage Least Squares				
Date: 08/16/22 Time: 15:13				
Sample: 1 110				
Included observations: 103				
Total system (balanced) observations 206				
	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(10)	0.131977	0.177933	0.741723	0.0592
C(11)	0.013855	0.010939	1.266578	0.0068
C(12)	-5.69E-07	1.30E-05	-0.043729	0.0652
C(13)	0.033829	0.006113	0.626422	0.0318
C(14)	0.024010	0.040210	0.597111	0.5511
C(15)	-0.043854	0.164775	-0.266147	0.0904
C(20)	1.361611	0.438919	3.102192	0.0022
C(21)	0.024749	0.034493	0.717511	0.0239
C(22)	0.102693	0.121277	0.846767	0.0882
C(23)	0.060685	0.010531	0.065023	0.0482
C(24)	0.007556	0.004168	1.812892	0.0214
C(25)	-2.516530	2.972715	-0.846543	0.0483
Determinant residual covariance		0.002970		
Equation: $KDIV=C(10)+C(11)*CR+C(12)*HG+C(13)*ROA+C(14)*DER$				
+C(15)*RSHM				
Instruments: CR HG ROA DER ROE PER C				
Observations: 103				
R-squared	0.601129	Mean dependent var	0.144369	
Adjusted R-squared	0.050359	S.D. dependent var	0.138328	
S.E. of regression	0.141768	Sum squared resid	1.949530	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.701060			
Equation: $RSHM=C(20)+C(21)*ROA+C(22)*DER+C(23)*ROE+C(24)*PER$				
+C(25)*KDIV				
Instruments: CR HG ROA DER ROE PER C				
Observations: 103				
R-squared	0.433269	Mean dependent var	1.336311	
Adjusted R-squared	0.507149	S.D. dependent var	0.476904	
S.E. of regression	0.585476	Sum squared resid	33.24984	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.486213			

Source: Processed Primary Data 2022

Based on the results of the structural equation output, it can be seen that there are 2 equations. The following is an explanation of each in 2 equations:

Results of equation I test:

The first equation is the equation used to determine the simultaneous effect on inflation and economic growth which is given as:

$$KDIV = C(10)+C(11)*CR+C(12)*HG+C(13)*ROA+C(14)*DER+C(15)*RSHM$$

Based on the above equation, the output of Eviews with the Two-Stage Least Square model is as follows:

$$KDIV=0.131976715523+0.0138548145904*CR-5.6869930382607*H+0.00382942966088*ROA+0.024009842368*DER-0.0438542486267*RSHM$$

And the output results of Eviews10 with the Two-Stage Least Square model are as follows:

$$KDIV=0.131976715523+0.0138548145904*CR-5.6869930382607*HG+0.00382942966088*ROA+0.024009842368*DER-0.0438542486267*RSHM$$

Based on the estimation results above, it is obtained that $R^2 = 0.601129$ which means that the variables CR, HG, ROA, DER, and RSHM are able to explain KDIV by 60.1% and the remaining 39.9% is influenced by other variables outside the estimates in the model.

Results of equation II test:

The second equation is the equation used to simultaneously determine the effect on inflation and economic growth which is given as:

$$RSHM=C(20)+C(21)*ROA+C(22)*DER+C(23)*ROE+C(24)*PER+C(25)*KDIV+e$$

Based on the above equation, the output of Eviews with the Two-Stage Least Square model is as follows:

$$RSHM=1.36161102166+0.0247487813732*ROA+0.102693361317*DER+0.000684752310791*ROE+0.00755614202223*PER-2.51652969634*KDIV$$

And the output results of Eviews10 with the Two-Stage Least Square model are as follows:

$$RSHM=1.36161102166+0.0247487813732*ROA+0.102693361317*DER+0.000684752310791*ROE+0.00755614202223*PER-2.51652969634*KDIV$$

Based on the estimation results above, it is obtained that $R^2 = 0.433269$ which means that the variables ROA, DER, ROE, PER, and KDIV are able to explain RSHM by 43,3% and the remaining 36,7% is influenced by other variables outside the estimates in the model.

Results of ARDL Panel Analysis

The calculation of the moderation test in this study uses the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) model, which is used to examine the effect of leadership and work environment on job satisfaction with motivation as the moderating variable.

Table 3: Results of ARDL Panel Test

Dependent Variable: D(RS)				
Method: ARDL				
Date: 08/20/22 Time: 12:32				
Sample: 2013 2021				
Included observations: 99				
Dependent lags: 1 (Fixed)				
Dynamic regressors (1 lag, fixed): ROE PER DER CR				
Fixed regressors: C				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Long Run Equation				
ROE	0.020807	0.000923	22.53389	0.0000
PER	0.010191	0.000188	54.28490	0.0000
DER	0.630955	0.001628	387.5205	0.0000
CR	0.154978	0.004241	36.54395	0.0000
Short Run Equation				
COINTEQ01	-0.231436	0.086221	-2.684218	0.0105
D(ROE)	-0.006752	0.004616	-1.462679	0.1514
D(PER)	0.000843	0.001956	0.431094	0.6687
D(DER)	-0.225353	0.051935	-4.339087	0.0001
D(CR)	-0.038394	0.022308	-1.721117	0.0930
C	0.462246	0.195841	2.360310	0.0232
Mean dependent var	0.010000	S.D. dependent var		0.171005
S.E. of regression	0.176779	Akaike info criterion		-3.670540
Sum squared resid	1.250034	Schwarz criterion		-1.952052
Log likelihood	271.8797	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.973512
*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model Selection.				

Source: Eviews' Output 2020

The ARDL Panel Model is accepted if it has a cointegrated lag, where the main assumption is that the coefficient value has a negative slope with a significant level of 5%. The results above indicate that the requirements for the ARDL Panel model used have been met: with a negative value, namely -0.23 and significant with a prob value <0.05, which is 0.0105, so it can be stated that the ARDL panel model used in this study is accepted. Based on the acceptance of the model, the data analysis was carried out by panel per company.

Table 4: Summary of ARDL Panel Output Results

Variabel	ABDA	AHAP	AMAG	ASBI	ASJT	ASRM	ASDM	LPGI	MREI	PNIM	PNLF	ShortRun
ROE	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
PER	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
DER	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
CR	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	
Cointeg	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	

Leading indicators of Stock Return in insurance companies in Indonesia include PT. Asuransi Bina Dartta, Tbk (ABDA), PT. Asuransi Harta Aman Pratama, Tbk (AHAP), PT.

Asuransi Multi Arta Guna, (AMAG), PT. Asuransi Bintang, Tbk (ASBI), PT. Asuransi Jasa Tania, Tbk (ASJT), PT. Asuransi Ramayana, Tbk (ASRM), PT. Lippo G Insurance, Tbk (LPGI), PT. Maskapai RI, Tbk (MREI), and PT. Panin Insurance, Tbk (PNIN). Thus, on a panel basis it turned out that all companies except PT. Panin Life, Tbk (PNLF) and PT. Asuransi Dayin Mitra, Tbk (ASDM) is able to be a leading indicator in influencing stock returns in insurance companies in Indonesia in short run and long run.

Thus, it is known that the leading indicator of insurance companies in Indonesia that is seen and reflected in Stock Return is ROE. This is because on the results of data processing, ROE is a variable that has a stable effect, which has a significant effect in the long and short term on Stock Return, which is assessed by the level of stability of the short run and long run in the results table.

ROE is the ratio of net income to equity which measures the rate of return of shareholders (Brigham & Houston, 2010:149). ROE shows the company's ability to generate profits that can be distributed to shareholders. The greater the ROE, the better because the company effectively uses equity to generate profits and vice versa. This is in accordance with the Signaling Hypothesis theory which states that investors perceive dividend changes to be captured as a signal of good earnings in the future (Atmaja, 2008: 287). Therefore, the company will increase dividend payments if there is an increase in profit. Research conducted by Elisya (2013) and Yudhanto & Aisjah (2011) on manufacturing companies proves that ROE has a significant positive effect on dividend policy (138 Journal of Business Economics Year 21, Number 2, and October 2016). Based on these statements, it is accepted that what is stated in hypothesis 1: ROE has a significant positive effect on dividend policy. Dividend policy can also be influenced by the use of debt in the company.

Optimal use of debt can increase the company's operational activities so that it will bring a higher level of profit to be distributed to shareholders. However, the use of debt that is too large can reduce dividend payments because the company has to pay off the interest expense and principal of the loan when it is due. This condition refers to the Trade-Off theory (Modigliani & Miller, 1963) which states that companies cannot use debt as much as possible because the higher the debt, the higher the risk of default, so the greater the possibility of bankruptcy (Hanafi, 2010: 309). Therefore, the amount of dividends to be distributed depends on the company's ability to manage its debt. The amount of the company's debt can be measured using the leverage ratio which is used to find out how well the company manages its debt portion. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is one of the leverage ratios used to assess debt by equity (Kasmir, 2010: 112). DER reflects the company's ability to manage the portion of debt with the capital owned by the company.

According to Horne and Wachowicz (2012), high ROE often reflects the company's acceptance of good investment opportunities and effective cost management. Thus the increasing ROE indicates the company has a good performance in managing its capital and can generate maximum profits and thus will increase prosperity for the owners of capital. So, companies that have high ROE will have a positive effect for investors to hunt for the company's stock returns and of course the stock returns will increase as well.

Arifin and Agustami (2016) who examined the effect of liquidity, solvency, profitability, market ratios, and firm size on stock prices suggested that the profitability variable proxied by return on equity had a positive effect on stock prices. Meanwhile, the study of Khoiriyah (2018) indicates that the Return on Equity variable partially also has a significant effect on stock prices. This means that the company's ROE that continues to grow will also have an impact on the company's stock price on the stock exchange in the form of price increases. The results of this study are in line with the studies of Arifin & Agustami (2016), and Khoiriyah (2018) which state that ROE has a significant effect on stock returns.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out using the simultaneous method, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. Based on the estimation results above, it can be shown that equation 1 is $R^2 = 0.601129$ which means that the variables CR, HG, ROA, DER, and RSHM are able to explain KDIV by 60.1% and the remaining 39.9% is influenced by other variables outside the estimate in model. Current Ratio has a positive and significant effect on the Dividend Policy of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange which are studied by researchers. Then the stock price has a negative and insignificant effect on the dividend policy of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange which are studied by researchers. ROA has a positive and significant effect on the dividend policy of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange which are studied by researchers. DER has a positive but not significant effect on the KDIV of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange under study. RSHM has a negative and insignificant effect on the KDIV of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange under study.
- b. Based on the estimation results above, it can be shown that $R^2 = 0.433269$ which means that the ROA, DER, ROE, PER, and KDIV variables are able to explain RSHM by 43.3% and the remaining 36.7% is influenced by other variables outside the estimates in the model. ROA has a positive and significant effect on RSHM. DER has a positive and not significant effect on RSHM. ROE has a positive and significant effect on the RSHM of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange under study. PER has a positive and significant effect on the RSHM of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange under study. KDIV has a negative and significant effect on the RSHM of insurance companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange under study.

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out using the ARDL Panel method, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. It is known that the Leading indicator of insurance companies in Indonesia that is seen and reflected in Stock Return is ROE. This is based on the results of data processing which indicates that the ROE variable is a variable that has a stable influence, which has a

significant effect in the long and short term on Stock Return, which is assessed by the level of short run and long run stability in the results table.

- b. Leading indicators of Stock Return in insurance companies in Indonesia include PT. Asuransi Bina Darta, Tbk (ABDA), PT. Asuransi Harta Aman Pratama, Tbk (AHAP), PT. Asuransi Multi Arta Guna, (AMAG), PT. Asuransi Bintang, Tbk (ASBI), PT. Asuransi Jasa Tania, Tbk (ASJT), PT. Asuransi Ramayana, Tbk (ASRM), PT. Asuransi Dayin Mitra, Tbk (ASDM), PT. Lippo G Insurance, Tbk (LPGI), PT. Maskapai RI, Tbk (MREI), PT. Panin Insurance, Tbk (PNIN), and PT. Panin Life, Tbk (PNLF). Thus, on a panel basis, it turns out that all of these variables are able to become leading indicators in influencing stock returns in insurance companies in Indonesia in the short run and long run.

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